

Distribution and transformation of zinc into discrete chemical pools in a Vertisol

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Abstract : The results of imperative laboratory experiment was revealed the incubation with 2.50, 5.00, 10.00 and 20.00 kg Zn ha⁻¹ significantly increased DTPA-extractable Zn, WS-Zn, CMPLX-Zn and ORG bound-Zn fractions at various periods of incubation (0, 15, 30, 60, 90 and 120 days) over control. Simultaneously, the DTPA-extractable Zn, WS-Zn, CMPLX-Zn and ORG bound-Zn fractions reduced with ascending periods of incubation (0 to 120 DAI) in all the Zn levels as well as in control. The incubation of 5.00, 10.00 and 20.00 kg Zn ha⁻¹ significantly increased EX-Zn, CRAMOX bound-Zn and CRYOX bound-Zn fraction at 0, 15, 30, 60, 90 and 120 DAI but all these fractions were also linearly decreased with ascending periods of incubation (0 to 120 DAI). The maximum residual-Zn content was obtained in soil incubated with 1.25 kg Zn ha⁻¹ at 0, 15, 30, 60, 90 and 120 DAI.

Keywords : Transformation, zinc, chemical pools, Vertisol.

Introduction

Zinc as a plant nutrient which has received considerable attention because of its occurrence in small quantities in the soil and criticality for plant growth. Though agricultural soils have good amount of total Zn which can meet the crop requirement for many years but its supply to crops may not be adequate for getting the healthy growth and higher yields. Several factors like soil characteristics, water management, manures and fertilizers influence the availability and transformation of both native and applied Zn. Among the soil characteristics like pH, organic matter, nature and amount of clay, CEC and CaCO₃ content play a vital role¹.

Zn exists in soil in different forms viz. primary and secondary minerals; insoluble inorganic and organic precipitates; soluble organic complexes; and exchangeable and adsorbed forms; and as soil solution Zn. These forms are in a state of dynamic equilibrium. The amount and rate of Zn solution determines the size of the labile Zn pool. The water soluble, exchangeable and complexed forms are believed to be in reverse equilibrium with each another, with equilibrium being established quickly². However, the study of the Zn distribution in various soil fractions provides a better understanding of Zn behaviour,

kinetics and rate of fixation and release in soil profile in relation to the transformation of Zn added to soil.

In order to understand Zn behaviour, the partition and distribution among active and non-active soil constituents and soil solution varying in their affinities and their contribution to the total Zn, dynamics and changes in relative solubility of different chemical forms far pertain at controlled electrochemical environment of Zn in soil profile i.e. fundamental soil chemistry of Zn, the comprehensive laboratory incubation study were taken up at room temperature for a period of 0, 15, 30, 60, 90 and 120 days.

Results and discussion

The results obtained from the present investigations as well as relevant discussion have been presented under following heads.

Effect of Zn incubation on DTPA-extractable Zn :

A close scrutiny of the data (Table 1) indicated that the incubation of 2.50, 5.00, 10.00 and 20.00 kg Zn ha⁻¹ significantly increased DTPA-extractable Zn at various periods of incubation (15, 30, 60, 90 and 120 days) over control. However, the application of 1.25 kg Zn ha⁻¹ was found to be significant in increasing DTPA-extract-

able-Zn only at initial stage (0 day) of incubation. Simultaneously, the DTPA-extractable-Zn reduced with ascending periods of incubation (0 to 120 DAI) in all the Zn levels as well as in control. This indicates that the release of Zn from native sources and fixation of applied Zn on absorbing site of clay occurred up to 120 days after incubation. The adsorbed Zn was subsequently released into solution phase. There was a decrease in the content of DTPA extractable-Zn with increase in days after incubation which was due to adsorption and fixation of added Zn by soil colloids, CaCO_3 , organic matter, primary and secondary minerals ultimately forming ZnCO_3 and Zn(OH)_2 ^{3,4}.

Effect of Zn incubation on water soluble (WS)-Zn fraction :

There was a significant increase in the WS-Zn fraction with the incubation of 2.50, 5.00, 10.00 and 20.00 kg Zn ha⁻¹ at various periods of incubation (0, 15, 30, 60, 90 and 120 days) as compared to control (Table 1). However, the WS-Zn fraction was linearly decreased with increasing time of incubation in all the increasing Zn levels. The magnitude of such decrease might be due to the increased in pH value of soil, which caused a decrease in the solubility of the native soil Zn^{5,6}, and precipitation of soluble Zn as hydroxide carbonate and its adsorption on the surface of manganese oxides and amorphous sesquioxides⁷.

Effect of Zn incubation on exchangeable (EX)-Zn fraction :

The results in Table 1 revealed that the EX-Zn fraction in soil increased by incubation with increasing levels of Zn over control but linearly decreased with ascending periods of incubation (0, 15, 30, 60, 90 and 120 days) in all the Zn levels. The application of 5.00, 10.00 and 20.00 kg Zn ha⁻¹ significantly increased EX-Zn fraction at all DAI. However, the application of 2.50 kg Zn ha⁻¹ was significant in increasing EX-Zn fraction at 0, 15, 30 and 60 DAI. The decreased in the content of EX-Zn fraction might be due to the microbial immobilization and formation of ZnCO_3 and $\text{Zn(CO}_3)_2\text{OH}_2$ ⁸. This could be also attributed to the increase in pH and relatively lower in organic carbon content with increasing time in the soil under incubation. The increased pH might have favoured precipitation of some amounts of Zn as hydroxides and

also its adsorption on the surface of freshly formed hydrated oxides of Fe and Mn, which are known to have a strong scavenging action for Zn because of their high specific surface area⁹.

Effect of Zn incubation on complexed (CMPLX)-Zn fraction :

Results (Table 1) showed that the amount of CMPLX-Zn fraction in soil was found to increase due to the incubation with increasing levels of Zn over control but linearly decreased with ascending periods of incubation (0, 15, 30, 60, 90 and 120 days) in the all Zn levels as well as in control. The application of 2.50, 5.00, 10.00 and 20.00 kg Zn ha⁻¹ significantly increased CMPLX-Zn fraction in soil as compared to control. The decreased in the content of CMPLX-Zn fraction may partly be due adsorption on the surface of the hydrated oxides of Fe and Mn. This could also be attributed to unfavorable soil pH and in the absence of low organic matter content as the CMPLX-Zn fraction constitutes mainly weakly organically bound pool of Zn^{10,11}.

Effect of Zn incubation on organically (ORG) bound-Zn fraction :

The application of increasing levels of Zn increased the ORG bound-Zn fraction in soil due to the incubation over control but decreased with ascending periods of incubation (0, 15, 30, 60, 90 and 120 days) in the all Zn levels. This has been shown in Table 1. The application of 2.50, 5.00, 10.00 and 20.00 kg Zn ha⁻¹ significantly increased ORG bound-Zn fraction over control but reduced with ascending time of incubation (0 to 120 days). This increase in ORG bound-Zn fraction is possibly due to the subsequent chelation by organic compound resulting from aerobic decomposition of soil organic matter. The declined trends towards latter period might be due to the decrease in stability of Zn organic complexes at the Eh of the soils attained at the prolonged submergence¹¹. Higher amount of this fraction may be due to the low rate of decomposition due low microbial activity associated with cool temperatures which eventually disappeared with the advancement of warm season due to increase in microbial activity^{12,13}.

Effect of Zn incubation on carbonate and amorphous oxides (CRAMOX) bound-Zn fraction :

The CRAMOX bound-Zn fraction in soil increased

Table 1. Influence of Zn incubation on DTPA-extractable Zn and various chemical forms of Zn in a Vertisol (data pooled over 2 year)

Levels of Zn (kg ha ⁻¹)	DTPA-extractable Zn and different fractions of Zn (mg kg ⁻¹)																	
	DTPA-extractable Zn				WS-Zn				EX-Zn									
	0	15	30	60	90	120	0	15	30	60	90	120	0	15	30	60	90	120
0 (Control)	DAI	DAI	DAI	DAI	DAI	DAI	DAI	DAI	DAI	DAI	DAI	DAI	DAI	DAI	DAI	DAI	DAI	DAI
1.25	0.55	0.53	0.51	0.50	0.49	0.48	0.053	0.051	0.053	0.049	0.048	0.046	0.46	0.44	0.43	0.42	0.41	0.38
2.50	0.60	0.58	0.56	0.52	0.51	0.49	0.056	0.054	0.053	0.051	0.050	0.048	0.50	0.49	0.47	0.46	0.45	0.41
5.00	0.71	0.68	0.65	0.63	0.60	0.57	0.076	0.071	0.066	0.065	0.064	0.061	0.66	0.64	0.62	0.59	0.57	0.53
10.00	1.06	1.03	0.95	0.91	0.87	0.83	0.091	0.086	0.083	0.080	0.079	0.078	1.01	0.99	0.95	0.89	0.85	0.80
20.00	1.51	1.48	1.43	1.40	1.36	1.32	0.110	0.105	0.101	0.096	0.093	0.089	1.53	1.48	1.44	1.39	1.36	1.31
Mean	1.92	1.87	1.82	1.79	1.73	1.68	0.125	0.121	0.118	0.116	0.114	0.111	1.81	1.76	1.71	1.66	1.59	1.55
SEm (±)	1.06	1.02	0.98	0.95	0.93	0.89	0.085	0.081	0.079	0.076	0.074	0.072	1.00	0.97	0.94	0.90	0.87	0.83
C.D. (P=0.05)	0.03	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.02	0.02	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.003	0.002	0.03	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.03
0.08	0.08	0.07	0.08	0.07	0.07	0.06	0.006	0.006	0.005	0.005	0.006	0.005	0.07	0.06	0.07	0.06	0.06	0.06
Levels of Zn (kg ha ⁻¹)	CMPLX-Zn				ORG-Zn				GRAMOX-Zn									
0 (Control)	0.97	0.86	0.77	0.68	0.62	0.59	2.63	2.58	2.54	2.50	2.47	2.45	3.32	3.29	3.25	3.23	3.22	3.20
1.25	1.03	0.92	0.80	0.70	0.63	0.60	2.73	2.67	2.59	2.53	2.49	2.45	3.41	3.35	3.30	3.27	3.36	3.21
2.50	1.31	1.21	1.08	1.01	0.93	0.89	3.54	3.41	3.29	3.11	2.96	2.91	4.36	3.98	3.71	3.47	3.79	3.29
5.00	1.93	1.76	1.54	1.44	1.38	1.34	5.03	4.89	4.77	4.66	4.55	4.49	5.30	4.75	4.54	3.98	4.98	3.59
10.00	2.49	2.22	2.00	1.84	1.73	1.65	6.44	6.09	5.92	5.82	5.63	5.56	6.24	5.87	5.57	5.26	5.87	4.73
20.00	3.09	2.83	2.69	2.59	2.47	2.39	7.18	6.93	6.75	6.62	6.51	6.39	7.57	7.17	6.66	6.23	4.07	5.69
Mean	1.80	1.63	1.49	1.37	1.29	1.24	4.59	4.43	4.31	4.20	4.10	4.04	5.03	4.73	4.50	4.24	4.10	3.95
SEm (±)	0.04	0.04	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.04	0.10	0.09	0.09	0.10	0.09	0.09	0.12	0.12	0.11	0.10	0.29	0.09
C.D. (P=0.05)	0.12	0.11	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.11	0.30	0.27	0.27	0.29	0.29	0.26	0.35	0.33	0.33	0.28	3.22	0.27
Levels of Zn (kg ha ⁻¹)	CRYOX-Zn				Residual-Zn				Total-Zn									
0 (Control)	4.35	4.28	4.20	4.09	4.05	3.97	63.22	63.40	63.67	63.98	64.16	64.33	75.00	74.91	74.91	74.95	74.96	74.97
1.25	4.65	4.60	4.50	4.35	4.19	4.09	63.29	63.57	63.89	64.23	64.59	64.78	75.66	75.65	75.59	75.58	75.62	75.58
2.50	5.08	4.91	4.73	4.49	4.27	4.14	61.14	62.02	62.65	63.48	63.96	64.38	76.16	76.23	76.14	76.19	76.13	76.21
5.00	6.70	6.68	6.32	6.18	6.06	5.92	57.42	58.22	59.26	60.23	60.60	61.20	77.48	77.38	77.45	77.46	77.31	77.42
10.00	8.38	8.22	8.12	8.04	7.95	7.86	54.73	55.94	56.74	57.43	58.21	58.79	79.91	79.93	79.90	79.88	79.96	79.99
20.00	9.57	9.39	9.24	9.14	9.00	8.88	55.56	56.71	57.70	58.49	59.46	59.97	84.91	84.92	84.87	84.85	85.00	84.98
Mean	6.46	6.34	6.19	6.04	5.92	5.81	58.22	59.98	60.64	61.30	61.83	62.24	78.18	78.16	78.14	78.15	78.16	78.19
SEm (±)	0.18	0.15	0.16	0.15	0.16	0.16	1.90	1.95	1.93	1.98	1.96	1.86	1.88	1.93	1.90	1.88	1.89	1.86
C.D. (P=0.05)	0.52	0.45	0.45	0.45	0.47	0.47	5.50	5.63	5.58	5.73	5.65	5.37	5.43	5.60	5.49	5.42	5.45	5.36

due to the incubation with increasing levels of Zn over control but linearly decreased with ascending periods of incubation (0, 15, 30, 60, 90 and 120 days) in all the Zn levels (Table 1). The CRAMOX bound-Zn fraction was found to be increased significantly with the incubation of 5.00, 10.00 and 20.00 kg Zn ha⁻¹ at 0, 15, 30, 60, 90 and 120 DAI. However, the incubation of 2.50 kg Zn ha⁻¹ in soil was significantly increased CRAMOX bound-Zn fraction only at initial stage (0 day), 15 and 30 DAI. The increase might be due to the fact that under reduction condition there is an increase in formation of hydrated oxides of Mn and Fe, the freshly formed compound which possess larger surface area and hence have strong adsorption capacity¹⁴. The Zn released from other bound forms might have held by Mn and Fe hydroxide resulting in increased content of CRAMOX bound-Zn fraction. The Mn oxide-Zn may also be attributed to the reduction in some crystalline form of Fe oxides and thus releasing some amount of occluded Zn for its subsequent adsorption on the hydrous oxide form¹⁵. The decreasing CRAMOX bound-Zn fraction with increasing incubation time might be due to decrease in redox potential of soils which caused the reduction of freshly formed manganic and ferric hydroxide resulting in the release of adsorbed Zn¹⁶.

Effect of Zn incubation on crystalline oxides (CRYOX) bound-Zn fraction :

The CRYOX bound-Zn fraction in soil was increased due to incubation with increasing levels of Zn over control but linearly decreased with ascending periods of incubation (0, 15, 30, 60, 90 and 120 days) in all the Zn levels as well as in control. The incubation of 5.00, 10.00 and 20.00 kg Zn ha⁻¹ significantly increased CRYOX bound-Zn fraction at 0, 15, 30, 60, 90 and 120 DAI. However, the soil incubated with 2.50 kg Zn ha⁻¹ was significant only at 0, 15 and 30 DAI (Table 1). The predominance of this fraction amongst all chemical fractions may be due to higher sesquioxides in Vertisol as compared to other crystalline clay minerals. Furthermore, the extractant (CBD-Citrate bicarbonate dithionate) might have attacked the crystalline lattice structure partially dissolving the Zn fractions associated with it. The decrease in CRYOX bound-Zn fraction with increasing time might be due to reason that under reduced condition, some of the crystalline sesquioxides may undergo transformation

to an amorphous form resulting in the release of a part of the Zn occluded by former and it's subsequent by a sorption latter¹⁷.

Effect of Zn incubation on residual-Zn :

The maximum residual-Zn content was obtained in soil incubated with 1.25 kg Zn ha⁻¹ at 0, 15, 30, 60, 90 and 120 DAI (Table 1). However, the minimum residual-Zn was recorded in soil incubated with 10.00 kg Zn ha⁻¹ at 0, 15, 30, 60, 90 and 120 DAI. This might be due to the conversion of some amount of labile Zn into non-labile form. There was increase in residual-Zn throughout incubation period. This might be due to application of Zn, which indicates considerable transformation of Zn to residual fraction¹⁸.

Effect of Zn incubation on total-Zn :

Perusal of data (Table 1) indicated that the application of 20.00 kg Zn ha⁻¹ significantly increased total-Zn at various periods of incubation (0, 15, 30, 60, 90 and 120 days) over control. However, the application of 1.25, 2.50, 5.00 and 10.00 kg Zn ha⁻¹ also increased total-Zn though non-significantly at various periods of incubation as compared to control. This might be due to application of Zn. Transformation of water soluble + exchangeable Zn fraction to other unavailable forms of Zn was higher in this soil because of alkaline pH, low organic matter status and presence of free CaCO₃¹⁹.

Percent contribution of different fractions of Zn to total-Zn in soil under incubated condition :

As revealed by data (Table 2) the fractions contributing to directly and positively to total-Zn are WS-Zn, EX-Zn, CMLPX-Zn, ORG bound-Zn, CRAMOX bound-Zn, CRYOX bound-Zn and residual-Zn at 0, 15, 30, 60, 90 and 120 DAI. The per cent contribution of all the fractions to total-Zn decreased with the increasing days of incubation (0 to 120 days), while the contribution of residual-Zn was maximum and increased with ascending days after incubation. Various fractions of Zn are in state of dynamic equilibrium and hence the results that the all the fractions viz. CMLPX-Zn, ORG bound-Zn, CRAMOX bound-Zn and CRYOX bound-Zn and residual-Zn contribute to total-Zn are reasonable. If comparatively unavailable forms like CMLPX-Zn, ORG bound-Zn, CRAMOX bound-Zn, CRYOX bound-Zn and residual-Zn are dominant in soil, these will definitely increase

Table 2. Per cent contribution of various chemical fractions of Zn to total-Zn at different days after incubation (data pooled over 2 year were used)

Levels of Zn (kg ha ⁻¹)	Different Zn fractions													
	0 DAI					15 DAI					Residual-Zn			
	WS-Zn	EX-Zn	CMPLEX-Zn	ORG-Zn	CRAMOX-Zn	CRYOX-Zn	Residual-Zn	WS-Zn	EX-Zn	CMPLEX-Zn		ORG-Zn	CRAMOX-Zn	CRYOX-Zn
0 (Control)	0.07	0.61	1.29	3.51	4.43	5.81	84.29	0.07	0.59	1.15	3.44	4.39	5.71	84.64
1.25	0.07	0.66	1.36	3.61	4.51	6.15	83.65	0.07	0.65	1.22	3.53	4.43	6.08	84.03
2.50	0.10	0.87	1.72	4.65	5.72	6.67	80.28	0.09	0.84	1.59	4.47	5.22	6.44	81.36
5.00	0.12	1.30	2.49	6.49	6.84	8.65	74.10	0.11	1.28	2.27	6.32	6.14	8.63	75.23
10.00	0.14	1.91	3.12	8.06	7.81	10.49	68.48	0.13	1.85	2.78	7.62	7.34	10.29	69.99
20.00	0.15	2.13	3.64	8.46	8.92	11.28	65.44	0.14	2.07	3.33	8.16	8.44	11.06	66.78
Mean	0.11	1.25	2.27	5.80	6.37	8.17	76.04	0.10	1.21	2.06	5.59	5.99	8.03	77.01
Levels of Zn (kg ha ⁻¹)														
	30 DAI					60 DAI								
0 (Control)	0.07	0.57	1.03	3.39	4.34	5.61	84.99	0.07	0.56	0.91	3.34	4.31	5.46	85.36
1.25	0.07	0.62	1.06	3.43	4.37	5.95	84.52	0.07	0.61	0.93	3.35	4.33	5.76	84.98
2.50	0.09	0.81	1.42	4.32	4.87	6.22	82.28	0.09	0.77	1.33	4.08	4.55	5.86	83.31
5.00	0.11	1.23	1.99	6.16	5.86	8.16	76.51	0.10	1.15	1.86	6.02	5.14	7.98	77.76
10.00	0.13	1.80	2.50	7.41	6.97	10.16	71.02	0.12	1.74	2.30	7.29	6.58	10.07	71.90
20.00	0.14	2.01	3.17	7.95	7.85	10.89	67.99	0.14	1.96	3.05	7.80	7.34	10.77	68.94
Mean	0.10	1.18	1.86	5.44	5.71	7.83	77.88	0.10	1.13	1.73	5.31	5.38	7.65	78.71
Levels of Zn (kg ha ⁻¹)														
	90 DAI					120 DAI								
0 (Control)	0.06	0.55	0.83	3.30	4.28	5.40	85.59	0.06	0.51	0.79	3.27	4.27	5.30	85.81
1.25	0.07	0.60	0.83	3.29	4.26	5.54	85.42	0.06	0.54	0.79	3.24	4.25	5.41	85.71
2.50	0.08	0.75	1.22	3.89	4.41	5.61	84.02	0.08	0.70	1.17	3.82	4.32	5.44	84.48
5.00	0.10	1.10	1.79	5.89	4.90	7.83	78.39	0.10	1.03	1.73	5.80	4.64	7.65	79.05
10.00	0.12	1.70	2.16	7.04	6.23	9.94	72.80	0.11	1.64	2.06	6.95	5.91	9.83	73.49
20.00	0.13	1.87	2.91	7.66	6.91	10.58	69.95	0.13	1.82	2.81	7.52	6.70	10.45	70.57
Mean	0.10	1.09	1.62	5.18	5.17	7.49	79.36	0.09	1.04	1.56	5.10	5.01	7.34	79.85

DAI - Days after incubation.

total-Zn and deplete the DTPA extractable-Zn⁶. Depleted levels of readily available Zn in soil could be replenished by the other pools of Zn²⁰. This would suggest that the DTPA extracts from WS-Zn and EX-Zn, while other fractions and residual-Zn adversely affect the amounts extracted by DTPA.

Experimental

Soil and its characteristics :

The present investigation was conducted under All India Coordinated Research Project on “Micro, secondary nutrients and pollutant elements in soils and plants”, during the two consecutive years 2010-11 and 2011-12, at the Department of Soil Science and Agricultural Chemistry, Jawaharlal Nehru Krishi Vishwa Vidyalaya, Jabalpur, Madhya Pradesh, India. The soil used for laboratory incubation study were clayey in texture (Sand-25.2, Silt-17.9 and Clay-56.7%), neutral in reaction (pH-7.1), non-saline (EC-0.27 dS m⁻¹), non-calcareous (2.70%), medium in organic carbon content (0.63%), low in available nitrogen (217.5 kg ha⁻¹), medium in available P (18.5 kg ha⁻¹) and K (330.1 kg ha⁻¹) and deficient in DTPA-extractable Zn (0.54 mg kg⁻¹). The soil falls under Vertisol and belongs to Kheri-series of fine montmorillonite, Hyperthermic family of *Typic Haplusterts* popularly known as “medium black soil”.

Laboratory incubation study :

100 g air-dried, ground in a wooden pestle and mortar and 2 mm sieved through a muslin cloth soil sample were taken in wide-mouth plastic incubation tubes of 250 ml capacity. The soils were treated with different levels of Zn (0, 1.25, 2.50, 5.00, 10.00 and 20.00 kg ha⁻¹) using ZnSO₄·7H₂O in the form of solution, which was mixed uniformly with soil and then incubated in laboratory at room temperature (23±5 °C) for a period of 0, 15, 30, 60, 90 and 120 days. It was replicated four times and laid out in completely randomized design. The moisture level of the soil was maintained at 60 per cent of its field capacity throughout. The soils were stirred occasionally to permit aeration. The soils were thereafter extracted by DTPA²¹ and sequentially extracted with different extractants for different forms of Zn²² after different periods (0, 15, 30, 60, 90 and 120 days after incubation). In all the extracts, concentration of Zn was deter-

mined by atomic absorption spectrophotometer (Varian AA240 model).

Forms of zinc in soil :

The soil samples were fractionated into various Zn fraction viz. water soluble, easily exchangeable, complexed, organically bound, Zn bound to carbonate and amorphous oxides (acid soluble) and Zn bounded to crystalline oxides (CBD-extractable) following sequential extraction scheme proposed by Edward Raja and Iyengar (1986) with slight modification (Fig. 1). Extraction with various reagents, prepared in all double distilled water using 1 : 4 soil-solution ratio, was carried out by shaking for one hour on a rotatory shaker, except for last step (crystalline iron oxide bound Zn). For this fraction, the soil residue from preceding (0.1 M HCl) fraction was suspended in 40 ml of 0.3 M sodium citrate (Na₃C₆H₅O₇·2H₂O) and 5 ml of 1 M NaHCO₃ solution.

Fig. 1. Flow sheet showing extraction mode to determine various soil fractions of zinc in soil.

The suspension (pH 7.3) was heated at 80 °C on a water bath for 15 min with addition of 1 g of sodium dithionite (sodium hydro-sulphite, Na₂S₂O₄) with rapid stirring²³. Soil suspension at different stages was centrifuged at 2700 rpm and filtered. Whereas, soil residue was used for next step, filtered from each stage was saved for the determination of Zn fraction on atomic absorption spectrophotometer. The residual Zn was determined by subtracting all fractions of Zn from total Zn content in soil.

Statistical analysis :

The data generated from the present study were analyzed statistically and to draw suitable inference as per standard ANOVA technique²⁴.

Conclusion

It is apparent from study that, all the Zn fractions in soil increased by incubation with increasing levels of Zn over control but linearly decreased with increasing periods of incubation in all the Zn levels as well as in control. The incubation of 2.50, 5.00, 10.00 and 20.00 kg Zn ha⁻¹ significantly increased DTPA-extractable Zn at various periods of incubation (0, 15, 30, 60, 90 and 120 days) over control. Simultaneously, the DTPA-extractable Zn, WS-Zn, CMPLX-Zn, ORG bound-Zn fractions and total-Zn reduced with ascending periods of incubation (0 to 120 DAI) in all the Zn levels as well as in control. The incubation of 5.00, 10.00 and 20.00 kg Zn ha⁻¹ significantly increased EX-Zn, CRAMOX bound-Zn and CRYOX bound-Zn fraction at 0, 15, 30, 60, 90 and 120 DAI. However, the soil incubated with 2.50 mg Zn kg⁻¹ was significant in increasing EX-Zn, CRAMOX bound-Zn and CRYOX bound-Zn fraction only at 0, 15 and 30 DAI but all these fractions were also linearly decreased with ascending periods of incubation (0 to 120 DAI). There was increase in residual-Zn throughout incubation period. The maximum residual-Zn content was obtained in soil incubated with 1.25 kg Zn ha⁻¹ at 0, 15, 30, 60, 90 and 120 DAI. The minimum residual-Zn was recorded in soil incubated with 10.00 kg Zn ha⁻¹ at 0, 15, 30, 60, 90 and 120 DAI.

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